

Quantum Computing vs Classical Computing: Unlocking New Possibilities in Computation and Industry

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1. Introduction

Quantum computing represents a transformative shift in how we approach computational problems. Unlike conventional computers, which rely on binary logic, quantum computers leverage the principles of quantum mechanics to explore a broader state space. This report outlines the key benefits quantum computing can offer beyond classical architectures, explores their real-world applications across domains, and discusses implications for fields such as healthcare, cybersecurity, optimisation, and cryptography.

2. Fundamentals of Quantum Computing

Quantum computers operate using quantum bits (qubits), which differ fundamentally from classical bits. While classical bits exist in a state of either 0 or 1, qubits can exist in a superposition of states, representing both 0 and 1 simultaneously. Additionally, quantum entanglement allows qubits to be interdependent, meaning the state of one qubit can instantaneously affect another, regardless of distance.

These properties enable quantum systems to process complex computations with parallelism unachievable by classical machines, offering potential exponential speed-up for specific problem classes (Gottesman, 2016).

3. Classical Computer Architecture

Conventional computers are based on deterministic logic, utilising transistors and diodes to process data using binary states. Information is encoded in bits (0 or 1), and instructions are executed sequentially or through parallel classical cores. While classical architectures have been optimised for general-purpose computing and scaled through Moore's Law, their capabilities are limited when handling combinatorially complex problems or vast unstructured datasets.

4. Comparative Analysis and Industry Applications

4.1 Computational Power and Efficiency

Quantum algorithms offer substantial advantages in solving NP-hard problems, optimisation tasks and complex simulations. In fields like genomics, materials science and financial modelling, quantum systems can explore vast solution spaces more efficiently.

For instance, quantum-assisted DNA sequencing and structural analysis of proteins can dramatically accelerate personalised medicine workflows (Mehta & MacDonald, 2020).

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4.2 Healthcare

Quantum computing presents several game-changing possibilities in healthcare:

¹ This report was originally written as a part of university coursework at the University of Westminster in March 2022.

- **Diagnostic Assistance:** Enhances early detection through improved image analysis (e.g., colon cancer detection through quantum-enhanced edge detection).
- **Precision Medicine:** Enables high-speed genetic analysis, aiding tailored treatment development.
- **Operational Optimisation:** Quantum algorithms streamline resource allocation and cost reduction in hospital logistics.

Studies have shown that early diagnosis can increase survival rates by up to 9x and reduce treatment costs 4-fold when cancer is detected at earlier stages (National Academies, 2019).

4.3 Financial Services and Optimisation

Quantum computers have demonstrated promise in:

- **Portfolio Optimisation:** Leveraging quantum annealing for navigating vast combinations in investment portfolios.
- **Credit Scoring and Fraud Detection:** Using enhanced sampling and machine learning integration to predict financial outcomes more accurately.
- **Logistics and Supply Chains:** Solving routing problems (e.g., vehicle routing and warehouse distribution) with high precision and speed.

Quantum annealers, such as those developed by D-Wave, enable efficient solution discovery in optimisation landscapes with many local minima.

4.4 Cryptography and Cybersecurity

Quantum computing introduces both risks and opportunities in security. Algorithms such as Shor's Algorithm can factor large numbers in polynomial time, posing existential threats to classical cryptosystems like RSA and ECC (Denning, 2019).

To address this, Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) and Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) have emerged as solutions:

- QKD enables unbreakable encryption via quantum entanglement.
- Quantum-resistant algorithms (e.g., lattice-based cryptography) are being developed to secure data against quantum-enabled adversaries (Fernandez-Carames & Fraga-Lamas, 2020).

Initiatives like the Quantum Resistant Ledger (QRL) exemplify next-generation secure frameworks for digital transactions.

5. Challenges and Outlook

While quantum computing offers transformative potential, it remains in its infancy:

- **Hardware Limitations:** Current qubit systems are prone to decoherence and require extreme operating conditions.
- **Algorithmic Maturity:** Many quantum algorithms are in early development and not yet scalable for large industrial deployment.
- **Integration Barriers:** Seamless integration with classical systems requires hybrid computational models and new programming paradigms.

Nevertheless, future architectures are likely to be **hybrid systems**, combining quantum accelerators with classical backbones for specialised tasks (Kommadi, 2020).

6. Conclusion

Quantum computers are not intended to replace classical systems but to complement them in specific domains where classical computation falls short. The benefits include:

- Exponential speed-up in targeted computations
- Breakthroughs in drug discovery, diagnostics, and data science
- Enhanced cybersecurity through QKD and PQC
- Unprecedented improvements in optimisation, prediction and simulation

Quantum computing is poised to reshape industries, offering automation, cost reduction and performance improvements previously unattainable.

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